

An Evaluation of the Implementation of the Model of Integrated Care for Type 2 Diabetes in two Community Health Organizations

GP/PN TOPIC GUIDE

- Thank participant, introduce researcher & study
- Outline information sheet, consent form, highlight permission to record interview
- Remind and emphasise that it is a study to understand the acceptability and feasibility of the integrated care service i.e., we want to know how to improve the service, how it works in real life practice – please be honest

Interviews will explore GPs and PNs experience of engaging with integrated diabetic services (CNS diabetes, Podiatrist, Dietitian).

Topic Prompts/ potential follow-on questions/rational

<i>Introduction</i>	
<i>How is diabetes care delivered in your practice?</i>	Numbers of patients, age range, type 1/2 , ad hoc, planned, integrated care?
<i>Have you seen an increased need for diabetes care over the course of work within GP practice?</i>	Is diagnosing diabetes a regular occurrence? What are the reasons for this increase in your opinion? Are people presenting earlier with diabetes? Is there more awareness of diabetes- or is the increase a direct result in lifestyle changes? Has Cycle of Care/CDM prog increased practices involvement in delivering Diabetes Care?
<i>What are the challenges to the delivery of care for diabetes within your practice?</i>	This questionnaire is related to the questionnaires that you may have completed, and allows for further development of the details captured in the questionnaire.
<i>Has the practice made any investments in diabetes care?</i>	This could be educational/or financial investments in diabetes care? Further

Integrated care team Questions :CNS

Podiatry

Dietician

How have these new services impacted on delivery of GP?

Have you in your practice engaged with the new services?

If not, are there reasons for not engaging?

Do you have a preference of where CNS clinics should be placed?

Has the CNS facilitate fast track access to the OPD?

Has the podiatrist facilitated fast track access to the complex foot clinic in the hospital?

How, in general, do you refer patients to the OPD clinic?

How does the CNS fill that gap in service (i.e. poor access to hospital and long waiting list).

Wish list for future diabetic care?

questions on diabetes cycle of care, and Chronic diseases management programme. Has it required additional Staffing –Admin for data returns, PN/GP to deliver it?

General questions to establish level of engagement with the integrated care team and awareness of who can be referred-some think the service is only for GMS/GPVC patients. Don't know that Mod/High risk can be referred to podiatry

Are CNS clinics based in your practice?

Have you increased fast tracking access to the OPD, through the integrated team?

Has there been any notable improvements?

Has there been any notable improvements to the referral process for patients with complex foot (disease), related diabetic foot complications.

Have you fast tracked any patients into the complex foot clinic?

Referral pathways

What would be the challenges of referral?

Barriers to referral?

Explore the value of the CNS, esp in relation to hospital referral, and waiting list etc?

General positional question for future issues.

Any further comments?

Unstructured space to allow for participants or researcher to return so some point made earlier or not made.